

SOME COMMENTS ON THE CREATION AND OPERATION OF THE TASHKENT RADIO STATION (1926-1930)

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Annotation: This article analyzes issues related to the creation of the Tashkent radio station and its activities in the first years.

Key words: radio, radio station, radioization process, hardware, programs, radio nodes, radio committee, information, radio waves, radio points.

The construction of a radio station in Tashkent began in 1926 [1]. Newspapers published in 1926 reported that a radio station was being built in the republic, how far the sound could reach and the construction process. The construction of a radio station in the republic was related not only to the enrichment of science and technology with new achievements, but also to the promotion of trade, agriculture, and culture [2].

The first radio station in Uzbekistan was located in Tashkent on February 11, 1927, in an old building consisting of five small rooms on "Novaya" street, in the low 13th house, and its first radio broadcast lasted only two hours [3]. It was broadcast on 526 meter medium wave (MW) at 18.00. On this day, Yoldosh Okhunboboev, the first president of the Uzbek SSR, announced the establishment of radio broadcasting in the republic at the Labor Palace in Tashkent [4].

The radio station included two studio radio centers, two broadcast nodes and two orchestras [5]. According to the information of E. Koksharov, head of Tashkent radio, on April 12, 1927, broadcasts were conducted in Russian, Uzbek, Turkmen, Kazakh and Tadjik languages [6].

At the beginning, Tashkent radio broadcasts three or four times a week: from 5 to 7 o'clock in Russian, from 7 to 9 o'clock in Uzbek [7]. Also, broadcasts from Tashkent reached far places. In particular, it was clearly heard in cities such as Irkutsk, Krasnoyarsk, Turukhansk, Tomsk, Omsk, Petropavlovsk, Irbit, Sverdlovsk, Kazan, Samara, Kushka, Marv, Kheva, Tortkol, Dushanbe [8].

On September 15, 1927, Central Asian VTsSPS (Vsesoyuznyy tsentralnyy sovet professionalnyx soyuzov - Central Soviet of All-Union Trade Unions) issued an order to immediately re-register radio receivers in the republic from October 1 to November 1. Those who had not installed a radio had until October 1, 1927 to apply for one. This application had to be approved by the chairman of the neighborhood committee. Citizens who did not register before the specified period were handed over to the relevant state authorities and had to pay a specified fine [9].

In 1927, broadcasts in Uzbek were conducted at the Tashkent radio center 3 times a week for four hours [10]. On September 30, 1930, the RV-11 long-wave radio station with a power of 20 kilowatt hours on a wave of 1,170 meters began to work in Tashkent. The

programs of this station reached Pamir and Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Kyrgyzstan, Khorezm and Karakalpakstan, as well as Afghanistan [11].

In the second half of the 1930s, special attention was paid to the broadcasting of Tashkent city and Tashkent region. For example, in 1935, receiving radio station No. 2, equipped with 30 short-wave receiving antennas and occupying 60 hectares of land, was launched in Dormon settlement of Tashkent region. Radio station No. 4, located on 16 hectares of land equipped with 15 antennas, was put into operation in Yalang'och settlement of Tashkent. In addition to the launch of receiving radio stations, transmission radio station No. 5 was built in Yunusabad region this year.

This radio station is located on 41 hectares of land, with 16 short-wave receiving antennas and 11 transmitting antennas with a power of 5 to 20 kW. As a result, radio communication channels were established to communicate with the capitals of all countries [12].

By 1950, the total number of radio stations in the Tashkent region will reach 15,400. 8,082 of them, that is, 5.4 percent, were in villages. In 1955, the number of radio stations was 56,400, 47,700 of which were located in villages. The number of radio stations in the republic has increased by 3.6 percent over the past 5 years as a result of the activities carried out in connection with the radioization of the republic. The number of radio points in the city of Tashkent itself increased from 22,205 thousand in 1950 to 43,700 by 1955. It increased by 1.9 percent over 5 years. 44 at the Okhunboboev cotton factory, 250 at the Chkalov factory No. 84, 1400 at the Textile Combine, 250 at the Tashtektilmash factory, 85 at the hemp production factory, 249 at the Tashkent Medical Institute, 20 at the FZO No. 11 school, 20 at the Mental Hospital, 20 radio points were installed at the Tashkent pharmaceutical institute, 17 at the 3rd hospital for pulmonary diseases, 30 at the Khilkovo cement plant, 10 at the home of war invalids, and 18 at the sanatorium named after Kaganovich [13].

After the completion of the radio station in Tashkent, the main issue faced by the government was the issue of technical and journalist personnel for broadcasting. For this reason, the Council of People's Commissars issued an order to select and hire radio workers from among party members working in various fields until January 10, 1927. On the basis of this order, in 1927, P. Bogdanov, Yu. Malchensky, A. Kirov, F. Andreev, A. Mereshchenko were employed in radio [14]. From 1927, separate departments were created in the radio committee. Departments of workers and cleaners will be established based on the staff given by the radio committee. In addition, paramilitary security units were established, all of which were armed [15]. As a result of the measures taken, the number of employees at the Tashkent radio station grew, and at the end of 1927, the number of employees in the departments of the radio station reached a total of 76 people [16].

In the early years, the radio crew consisted of random people, many of whom were educated or amateurs [17]. Most of the staff selected from various fields for broadcasting and preparing programs on the radio were teachers [18], there was no staff capable of performing the duties of announcers, so the duties of announcers were performed by performers of various arts. The main host of Uzbek-language broadcasts was Yunus Rajabi, an artist and academician who served in Uzbekistan [19].

Taking this into account, the July 1928 Plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU (b) discussed the problems of "expanding measures" for personnel training. As a result, more than 30 technical schools and several higher educational institutions will be established. One

of them was the Technical College of Communication, which started working in Tashkent in July 1930. According to the plan, the technical school was intended to prepare personnel with special secondary technical education for the communication enterprises of the entire Central Asian republic [20.]

In January 1928, the Uzbek department was established on the radio, and its first announcer was Nazirkhan Kamolov. Nazirkhan Kamolov worked as a senior teacher at the Osh State Pedagogical Institute. Nazirkhan Kamalov was invited to the radio by Sumbatov, the head of the Russian department of the Tashkent radio station. From 1928, Nazirkhan Kamolov worked as an announcer and head of the Uzbek department of the radio until June 1928. During this short time, N. Kamolov will carry out work on expanding the ranks of the staff of the Tashkent radio broadcasting station. For example, the line of artists in the Old City brings its members to the radio, and musical and literary drama troupes were formed at the radio center.

They were led by Rizqi Rajabi [21], Yunus Rajabi [22] and Abdulhaq Sultanov. Concert programs are organized on the radio. Concert programs were conducted with the help of talented artists Yunus Rajabi, Rizqi Rajabi, O.Imomkhojaev and later Mulla Toychi Tashmuhammedov [23].

Hojimurad Avazkhojaev and Fatima Yunusova, who were among the initiators of radio broadcasting in our republic, had a special place. After returning to Osh in June 1928, Hajimurad Avazkhojaev N. Kamolov worked as a department head. Fatima Yunusova was one of the first female presenters of the republican radio, and listeners eagerly awaited her broadcasts [24].

In the late 20s and 30s of the 20th century, 12 radio newspapers in five languages were broadcast on Tashkent radio, which shows the extent of the work done in this regard. For example, radio newspapers with the names "Rabochiy" in Russian, "Struggle for Cotton", "Liberated Women" in Uzbek, "Tractor" in Kazakh, "Kolkhoz" in Kyrgyz and other names are regularly broadcast [25].

An analysis of radio news broadcasts during this period shows that the main broadcasts were devoted to political issues, followed by agricultural and cotton cultivation and maintenance. Another noteworthy point is that these broadcasts are organized in the form of lectures and interviews with the participation of experts in the fields [26]. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals[27].

In conclusion, it should be noted that Tashkent radio served as a basis for the creation of other regional radios of the republic. It can be witnessed that this is evident in the activities of the regional radios, which were deliberately established in the following years.

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